

STRESS ANALYSIS ON UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES
WITH DOUBLE SURFACE NOTCHES *

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ABSTRACT

The unidirectional composites with multiple surface notches exist in many structures, hence it is essential to study the effect of these multiple surface notches on the mechanical behavior of the unidirectional composites for the sake of structure safety. In this paper, stress analysis on the unidirectional composites with double surface notches in axial tensile loading is discussed using variational approach. Two types of double surface notches, common side and un-common sides respectively, are considered here. The distributions of stresses, displacements and stress concentration factors for the composites studied are given. With analysing the result computed, the interacting rule between double surface notches for the composites is explored.

KEYWORDS: Unidirectional Composites ; Double Surface Notches ; Variational Approach ; Stress Analysis ; Unidirectional Loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

The unidirectional fiber reinforced composites have now applied successfully to the fields of the automobile manufacture and so on for their excellent mechanical behavior. It is known that the fiber reinforced composites are easy damaged, it is possible for them to give rise to some notches in curing, processing and using, and surface notch is one of the major form in these notches. Hence stress analysis on the composites with surface notch is significance for structure design and safety evaluation.

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Because there are double surface notches or more in some composites, it is necessary to study the interacting rule between double surface notches. This is also the objective of this work. The unidirectional composites are generally treated as inhomogeneous and anisotropic materials. The shear-lag analysis presented by Hedgepeth [1] is a strong tool solving this kind of problem. Zhao and others [2-3] successfully studied the stress states on the unidirectional composites with a single surface notch, employed the shear-lag analysis. To solve this problem, a variational approach was also presented on the basis of the shear-lag assumptions in [4-5]. Both the shear-lag analysis and variational approach had the same precision computed, later was better than former in volume computed. In this paper, the above variational approach is employed to analyse the stress state on the multilayer composites with double surface notches in uniaxial loading.

2. FORMULATION

The general models considered for multilayer unidirectional composites with double surface notches, common side and un-common sides respectively, are shown in Fig.1(a,b). There are $M \times N$ sticks of equal spaced parallel fibers in a three dimension matrix. The spacind distance between fibers is b . The cross sectional area of fiber is a^2 . The fiber and matrix are linear elastic, E and G are Young's modulus of the fiber and shear modulus of the matrix, respectively. it is assumed that the fiber carries axial stress, and the matrix sustains shear stress only. The breakages in the fibers are in a plane, and the cross-section of double surface notches are two rectangles as shown in Fig.1(a,b).

Fig.1 Cross-section view of unidirectional composites with double surface notches

Then, the principle of minimum potential energy (*P M P E*) for a unidirectional laminate subjected to uniform axial load at the end of each fiber can be given as

$$\delta \Pi_p (U_{m,n}(X)) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$U_{m,n}(X) = 0 \quad (\text{unbroken fibers}). \quad (2)$$

The potential energy can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_p = & \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \left\{ \int_0^L \left[a^2 E (dU_{m,n}/dX)^2 + aG (U_{m,n} - U_{m+1,n})^2 / (2b) + \right. \right. \\ & aG (U_{m,n} - U_{m,n+1})^2 / (2b) + G (U_{m,n} + U_{m,n+1} - U_{m+1,n} - U_{m+1,n+1})^2 \\ & \left. \left. + (U_{m,n} + U_{m+1,n} - U_{m,n+1} - U_{m+1,n+1})^2 \right] / 8 \right\} dX - P_{m,n}^0 \cdot U_{m,n}(L) \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where $U_{m,n}(X)$ is the displacement for fiber (m,n) along the X-direction, $P_{m,n}^0$ is the load at the end of fiber (m,n) along the X-direction and L is a half length of the laminate.

Using the *PMPE*, the computation may be made approximately. Assuming that axial displacement $U_{m,n}(X)$ can be expanded in a power series as

$$U_{m,n}(X) = \sum_{s=0}^T A_s^{m,n} (X/L)^s \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } A_0^{m,n} = 0 \quad (\text{unbroken fibers}) \quad (5)$$

$$A_1^{m,n} = 0 \quad (\text{broken fibers}). \quad (6)$$

This axial displacement function evidently satisfies the displacement boundary conditions and a part of the stress boundary condition, axial stress zero at the breakage of the fibers over notch regions. Application of eqs.(1) and (2) yields a system of linear algebraic equations for determining the parameters $A_s^{m,n}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{GL}{s=0} \sum_{s=0}^T \frac{1}{s+s'+1} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (A_s^{m-1,n-1} - A_s^{m-1,n+1} - A_s^{m+1,n-1} - A_s^{m+1,n+1}) \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{a}{b} (A_s^{m-1,n} + A_s^{m,n-1} + A_s^{m,n+1} + A_s^{m+1,n}) + \left[2(1+2a/b) + \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. \frac{a^2 E s s' (s+s'+1)}{L^2 G \cdot (s+s'-1)} \right] A_s^{m,n} \right\} - P_{m,n}^0 = 0 \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $A_0^{m,n} = 0$ (unbroken fibers) (8)

$A_1^{m,n} = 0$ (broken fibers) (9)

$ss'/(s+s'-1) = 0$ ($s=0$ or $s'=0$) (10)

s' varies from 1 to T for unbroken fibers, and from 0 to T for others. Once $A_s^{m,n}$ are determined, the distributions of the stresses, displacements and stress concentration factors for the composites with double surface notches may be get. In this paper, the stress states for two types of the composites with double surface notches are computed, the results computed are analysed and discussed.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the material and geometric parameters for the unidirectional compositess are given in Table 1. $P_{m,n}^0 = 1 N$ is considered throughout this computation.

Table 1. MATERIAL AND GEOMETRIC PARAMETERS

Parameter	E	G	a	b	L
Value	138GP	1.28GP	$10^{-4} m$	$4 \times 10^{-5} m$	$10^{-2} m$

3.1 Double Common Side Surface Notches The displacement and stress distributions are computed numerically in the composites for notch length $H = 8$, notch depth $K = 2$ and various distance S between two notches. Fig.2 shows the distribution of axial stress of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches or at $X = 0$. With observing Fig.2 , it is found that there are stress concentration near the surface notches. The maximum axial stress concentrations occur at lateral sides near notches and at front of notch depth sides, i.e. fibers A and D, respectively, as shown in Fig.1. The

corresponding axial displacements at $X = 0$ are shown graphically in Fig.3. The maximum notch opening displacements still occur at the centre of

Fig.2 Axial stress of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches

Fig.3 Axial displacement of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches

the surface layer over notch regions. The above two results are the same as those for a single surface notch. Figs.4 and 5 respectively give variations of λ_a and λ_d with dimensionless distance S/H , where λ_a and λ_d are stress concentration factors at fibers A and D, respectively. It is told by Fig.5 that if distance S between double surface notches is less than notch length H , the axial stress concentration factor in fiber A is large compared with that for a single surface notch, and is the same as that with S increasing. Fig.5 reflects the effect of the ratio between S and H on the axial stress concentration factor in fiber D, and when the ratio is more than 0.5, its effect may be ignored. The result computed indicates that the position where the maximum axial stress concentration factors at the front of notch depth sides occurs is still at fiber D independent of the ratio between S and H .

Fig.4 Stress concentration factor at fiber A versus dimensionless distance

Fig.5 Stress concentration factor at fiber D versus dimensionless distance

Fichter studied the stress distribution for the composites with double through notches [6]. It is known that a through notch is one special form of surface notches. By variational approach in this paper, the stress distribution for the composites with double through notches and $S = 8$ is computed, and is compared with that given by Fichter, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. RESULTS COMPUTED IN THIS PAPER AND GIVEN BY FICHTER

Notch Length H	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
λ This paper	1.30	1.58	1.82	2.04	2.26	2.47	2.67	2.8
λ^a Fichter	1.34	1.61	1.86	2.08	2.29	2.49	2.68	2.8

It is found that the result in this paper agree with that given by Fichter

3.2 Double Un-common Sides Surface Notches The distributions of stress and displacement are computed in the composites with double un-common sides surface notches for notch length $H = 8$, notch depth $K_1 = 1, 2$ and $K_2 = 1, 2$, and various distance S between double surface notches. Fig.6 and.7 display the axial displacement and stress distribution of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches, respectively. The maximum axial stress concentration factors occur at fiber A or D, and the maximum notch

Fig.6 Axial displacement distribution of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches

Fig.7 Axial stress distribution of fibers in the cross-section with surface notches

opening displacement occurs at the center of surface layer over each notch region. These results are still the same as those for a single surface notch. Shown in Fig.8 and Fig.9 are the relations of stress concentration factors λ_a and λ_d with distance S between two surface notches for various notch depths, respectively. With analysing the above two figures, it is

Fig.8 Stress concentration factor at fiber A versus distance between two surface notches

Fig.9 Stress concentration factor at fiber D versus distance between two surface notches

obtained that S has a critical value S_c when $S < S_c$, the axial stress concentration factors for double surface notches are large compared with those for a single surface notch; when $S > S_c$, each notch can be considered independently with little loss of accuracy. It is found

$$S_c = 2 (K_1 + K_2) \quad (11)$$

8. CONCLUSIONS

The maximum axial stress concentration factors occur at lateral sides near notches and at front of notch depth sides, i. e. fiber A and D, respectively, for whatever the composites with double common side or un-common sides surface notches. This point is the same as that for a single surface notch. The distance S between two surface notches has a critical value S_c . If $S > S_c$, each notch can be considered independently with little loss of accuracy. It is found $S_c = H$ for double common side surface notches, and $S_c = 2 (K_1 + K_2)$ for double un-common sides surface notches.

5. REFERENCES

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